

Supplementary File

From One to Many: How Active Robot Swarm Sizes Influence Human Cognitive Processes

Julian Kaduk¹, Müge Cavdan², Knut Drewing², & Heiko Hamann¹

¹ University of Konstanz, Department of Computer and Information Science, Cyber-Physical Systems Research Group, Konstanz, Germany

² Justus Liebig University, Department of Experimental Psychology, Hap-Lab Research Group, Giessen, Germany

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ORCID of the authors:

Julian Kaduk: 0000-0003-3338-1850

Müge Cavdan: 0000-0003-3575-3849

Knut Drewing: 0000-0001-6161-5912

Heiko Hamann: 0000-0002-2458-8289

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Questionnaire

1. Estimate the duration of the task and indicate it on the timeline:

2. How quickly did the time pass for you during the task:

very slow

slow

normal

fast

very fast

3. How were you feeling during the task?

sad

neutral

happy

4. Rate your level of arousal during the task:

calm

neutral

active

5. Now put yourself back in the shoes of the task you have just completed. Were you in the “flow”?

not at all

very

6. The requirements of the task were:

too low

just right

too high